

Table S2 Baseline characteristics of control subjects and enrolled HCM patients

	Donor	HCM	P-value
	Control	Patients	
	(n=6)	(n=6)	
Clinical/demographic features			
Male, n (%)	6 (100)	5 (83)	1
Age, years	52±6.83	53±3.88	0.7367
Heart function classification, n (%)			
NYHA class I	6 (100)	0	<0.0001
NYHA class II	0	0	
NYHA class III	0	6 (100)	<0.0001
Family history of HCM	NO	NO	
Hypertension, n (%)	0 (0)	6 (100)	<0.0001
Drug treatment			
β-blockers	NO	YES	<0.0001
Calcium channel blockers	NO	YES	<0.0001

NYHA : New York Heart Association